

Engage_IoT

Engagements with the Internet of Things

REPORT 1

USE OF IOT DEVICES

IN PORTUGAL:

STATISTICAL DATA

December 2022

Summary

[Engage IoT](#) is a research project funded by the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (EXPL/SOC-SOC/1375/2021). The core aim of this project is to understand how social actors (producers, consumers, regulators) engage with a new kind of technology (IoT), from the macro level of sociotechnical imaginaries to the micro level of practices of use.

This report summarises statistical data available regarding the use of domestic IoT devices in Europe and Portugal. The source is Eurostat's Survey on ICT usage in households and by individuals, carried out in 2020 and 2022. The data presented here concerns the use of IoT by type of device, by country, and by sociodemographic variables and the reasons not to use IoT. Overall, Portugal has a fairly low usage of IoT devices, with the exception of internet-connected TVs. Users of IoT devices are mainly young, male, with high education levels and high income, living in cities and working on ICT. Among the main reasons for the non-use of IoT are the perception that these devices are unnecessary and their high cost.

Introduction

Eurostat's [Survey on ICT usage in households and by individuals](#) collects information on the evolution of the Internet Society in Europe since 2002. This instrument has been crucial in tracing the diffusion of ICT technologies in households, monitoring the changes in Internet uses, and gauging who has access to the Internet (and how). In 2020, questions about the use of IoT devices were first introduced; in the 2022 edition of the survey also included questions in IoT.

Two main topics are addressed in this section of the questionnaire: the use of IoT devices and the barriers to the use of IoT. The database provides information for the EU27 countries (and a few more outside the EU) and the information is discriminated by type of IoT devices and by type of user (sex, age, education, household income, occupation, etc.). Eleven types of IoT devices are considered:

1. thermostat, utility meters, lights, plug-ins or other internet-connected solutions for energy management for their home
2. home alarm system, smoke detector, security cameras, door locks or other internet-connected security/safety solutions for their home
3. home appliances such as robot vacuums, fridges, ovens, coffee machines
4. virtual assistant in the form of a smart speaker or of an app
5. internet-connected TV
6. internet-connected game console
7. internet-connected home audio system, smart speakers
8. smart watch, a fitness band, connected goggles or headsets, safety-trackers, internet-connected accessories, internet-connected clothes or shoes
9. devices for monitoring blood pressure, sugar level, body weight or other internet-connected devices for health and medical care
10. toys connected to the internet, such as robot toys (including educational) or dolls

11. car with built-in wireless internet connection

This report focuses on the use of IoT devices in Portugal, although some comparisons with EU27 and its individual countries are made. All figures are given as percentage of individuals. Data was first extracted from Eurostat in March 2022 and analysed in May 2022 (2020 data) and then in December 2022 (2022 data).

Use of IoT devices

The IoT device most commonly used in Portuguese and European households is an internet-connected TV (Figure 1). Around half of the surveyed individuals stated that they had used one in the previous year. This is hardly surprising since most TV sold currently are 'smart-TVs' with an internet connection by default. They are particularly useful for accessing streaming platforms and often can also be used to operate other IoT devices in the home. Similarly, internet-connected game consoles and audio systems also rank high in the list of IoT devices used in Portugal (25% and 13% respectively) and in Europe (20% and 17% respectively). Internet-connected accessories such as smart watches and fitness bands are also becoming quite common: 28% of users in Portugal and 25% in Europe. Some devices are more popular in Europe than in Portugal: such is the case of virtual assistants (13% of users in Europe for just 7% in Portugal), internet-connected thermostats or utility meters (10% in Europe, 6% in Portugal) or internet-connected alarm systems and cameras (9% in Europe, 6% in Portugal). IoT domestic appliances (fridges, ovens, vacuum cleaners) have less than 10% of users and toys are the least used kind of internet-connected devices. Overall, it can be said that usage of IoT devices in the domestic sphere, other than TVs, is fairly low.

Figure 1 Percentage of individuals who used IoT devices in Portugal and the EU27 in 2022

Source: Eurostat, 2022

Considering changes over this relatively short period of time in Portugal (Figure 2), there was an increase in the use of almost all devices. This is particularly noticeable in the case of smart watches and fitness bands (from 19% to 28% of users), domestic appliances (more than doubled) and internet-connected TVs (a rise from 44% to 52%). Though in some cases this can be due to the replacement of older devices (e.g. TVs, game consoles, cars, meters, washing machines) by modern models that have an internet connection by default, in others it does represent a purposeful adoption of IoT devices (e.g. smart watches, medical devices, robot cleaners).

Figure 2 Percentage of individuals who used IoT devices in Portugal in 2020 and 2022

Eutostat 2020 and 2022

Figures 3 to 10 provide an overview of the percentage of users of different IoT devices across Europe. It is noticeable that The Netherlands leads the ranking in terms of percentage of users in almost all devices, followed by Estonia and the Nordic countries. Spain joins the leading group when it comes to smart TVs, virtual assistants and medical devices. Overall, Eastern European countries and Greece have lower rates of adoption of IoT, but the same can be said for Italy in terms of smart thermostats, home appliances and smart watches. Users of smart thermostats reach 66% in the Netherlands and Slovenia and Austria have also high percentages of users. Smart home appliances are more popular in Malta (20%), Norway (19%) and Slovenia (18%). Smart watches and fitness bands have a high proportion of users in Czechia (49%). Medical devices are more frequent in Denmark (15%).

Country differences in the use of IoT devices can be attributed partly to the availability (and price) of high-speed Internet connections at home, but other social, economic and cultural factors may also play a role. According to Del Rio et al. (2021) local cultures shape the use of smart home devices, in particular along the dimensions of differentiated social uses, assisting with ageing, pursuing luxury and status, attaining a more resilient home, enthusiasm for new technologies and achieving trust, safety and security.

Figure 3 Internet-connected TV, game console, audio system

Figure 4 Thermostats, smart meters

Figure 5 Smart watch, fitness band

Figure 6 Virtual assistants

Source: Eurostat, 2022

Figure 7 Home alarm systems, cameras

Figure 8 Home appliances

Figure 9 Medical devices

Figure 10 Toys

Source: Eurostat, 2022

Use of IoT devices by sociodemographic characteristics

Rates of use of IoT devices vary according to sociodemographic characteristics, as other studies have shown (Amirthalingam et al. 2018, Kasilingam and Krishna 2020). In almost all types of IoT devices (Figure 11), there is a linear negative association between use and age: younger age groups (particularly in the 16 to 24 years bracket) have higher rates of IoT use, whereas older age groups (particularly above 65 years) have the lowest. The few exceptions are smart watches and fitness bands (used in a slightly higher proportion by 25 to 34 years olds) and cars with wireless connections (used in a higher proportion by 45 to 54 year olds). Home alarm systems and surveillance cameras are also more commonly used by 35 to 44 year olds.

Figure 11 Use of IoT devices by age group in Portugal in 2022

Source: Eurostat, 2022

Figures for the use of IoT devices by level of education (Figure 12) show that there is a linear positive relative: individuals with higher levels of education tend to use IoT more. However, the distance is larger between low and medium levels than between middle and high levels of education. This is necessarily associated to the skills needed to operate such devices, but also to disposable income. According to Hargreaves et al. (2018), IoT devices place significant demands on their users, requiring forms of adaptation and familiarisation , with little available support.

Figure 12 Use of IoT devices by level of education in Portugal in 2022

Source: Eurostat, 2022

Differences by sex can also be noticed (Figure 13). In all kinds of IoT devices, women tend to use them a bit less than men, including domestic appliances, which goes against observed trends in time use surveys, that show women spend more time on domestic chores than men (Perista 2017). This is perhaps due to these objects being perceived as technological devices more than domestic appliances. The largest difference is observed in smart watches and fitness bands.

Figure 13 Use of IoT devices by sex in Portugal in 2022

Source: Eurostat, 2022

The relation between use of IoT devices and household income is also linear and positive (Figure 14): individuals living in households with higher incomes tend to use more all kinds of IoT devices. This is surely associated with the cost of acquiring such devices. This question was not included in the 2022 survey, so data for 2020 is shown.

Figure 14 Use of IoT devices by household income in Portugal in 2020

Source: Eurostat, 2020

Regarding the use of IoT devices by individuals living in households with and without children (Figure 15), higher rates of use are found in the former, in particular when it comes to internet connected TVs and game consoles, smart watches and fitness bands and of course toys. However, this can be strongly associated with the age group of respondents, as seen above, more than the presence of children in the household.

Figure 15 Use of IoT devices in household with or without children in Portugal in 2022

Source: Eurostat, 2022

Figure 16 Use of IoT devices by type of habitat in Portugal in 2022

Source: Eurostat, 2022

The use of IoT devices is unevenly distributed also in geographical terms (Figure 16). Individuals living in cities have higher rates of use than individuals living in towns and suburbs and particularly in rural areas. This can be related to the income variation, but also to accessibility of purchasing such devices.

Figure 17 shows that IoT devices are used in higher proportion by students, followed by employed people. This is of course connected with age and income groups.

Figure 17 Use of IoT devices by labour situation in Portugal in 2022

Source: Eurostat, 2020

Finally, survey data shows that working in ICT has a bearing on the adoption of IoT. In all kinds of IoT products, ICT workers have a higher percentage of users. This is probably associated with the skills need to instal and operate these devices and access to information about them.

Figure 18 Use of IoT devices by occupation in ICT

Source: Eurostat, 2022

Reasons for not using IoT devices

Just as important as the percentage of users of IoT devices is the amount of individuals who decide not to use them and their reasons. According to this survey, 62% of Europeans and 66% of Portuguese individuals surveyed in 2022 did not use any IoT device in the previous year. In Portugal, this proportion has slightly risen in the past two years (from 63% in 2020).

Across Europe (Figure 19), the lowest rate of non-users is found in the Netherlands (just 21%). With about 50% of non-users are Norway, Malta, Sweden, Spain and Estonia. The highest percentage of non-IoT users is in Romania (77%), followed by Latvia, other Eastern European countries and Greece.

Figure 19 Percentage of individuals who have not used any IoT device in 2022

Source: Eurostat 2022

Survey respondents were asked to state their reasons for not using IoT devices (Figure 20). The most common answer pertains the absence of need to use such devices (a little over 40% of individuals both in Europe and in Portugal). But Portuguese respondents are also concerned with the costs (25%), security (20%) and privacy and protection of personal data (19%) of such devices, far above the European average. Lack of compatibility between devices worries 17% of respondents, 14% are not even aware they exist and 13% consider they lack the necessary skills to use them.

Across Europe, lack of need is more commonly stated in Poland, Germany, Finland and Czechia, high costs are invoked mostly by Croatia and Romania, and concerns about security and about privacy and personal data in Austria, Finland, Croatia and Spain. Lack of compatibility concerns mostly Latvians, Greeks, and Finish respondents. Higher percentages of individuals unaware of IoT devices can be found in Romania, Slovenia and Spain, whereas lack of skills is more commonly stated in Croatia, Belgium, Spain and Finland. In all these reasons, Portugal is almost always in the leading group of countries.

However, this list covers only a limited number of reasons for foregoing IoT devices, whereas Sovacool and Del Rio (2020) identified quite a few more, such as technical

reliability and obsolescence, usability, wasteful consumption, loss of personal control, lack of home ownership, fear of new technology, etc.

Figure 20 Reasons for not using IoT devices in Portugal and the EU27 in 2022

Source: Eurostat, 2022

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